

A STUDY ON THE NEW GST RATES – ANALYSIS OVER 47TH GST MEETING

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ABSTRACT:

GST is an indirect tax that comes into force in 2017. Although the GST Law was implemented in 2017, the current fluctuations in GST rates harm the general public, particularly the middle and lower classes in short term, but it will help the nation in long term. We attempted to demonstrate the impact of the 47th GST meeting changes on society by taking into account the past and current situation. This paper concentrates on the comparison of current GST Framework, old GST and indirect tax. It describes the GST impact on Indian economy in brief. The purpose of this research is to better understand the impact of the new GST rates on various segments of society, as well as to analyze the impact of GST on common man. The research design used in this study includes brief Highlights of the 47th GST Council meeting, Observation, different Economists' Opinions, Published Articles and related websites.

Keywords: GST, TAX RATE, GENERAL PUBLIC, 47TH GST COUNCIL MEETING, MANGALORE RESIDENTS.

INTRODUCTION:

The Goods and Services Tax (GST) is an indirect tax that was implemented in India on July 1, 2017. It modified multiple cascading taxes levied by the central and state governments. GST is viewed as an indirect tax for the entire country, with the goal of transforming India into a unified common market. It is a tax levied on the purchase, manufacture, and use of goods and services. It is a single tax levied on the sale of goods and services from the manufacturer to the customer [1]. The GST bill has an extensive influence on nearly every aspect of the country's business entity, such as product and service pricing, supply chain optimization, IT, accounting, and tax collection systems [2]. The GST reform is expected to cause substantial improvements in the Indian economy. There are numerous types of taxes levied on goods and services by the federal and state governments. This paper looks into the implications of GST on the Indian economy [3]. This taxation system furnished the Indian economy with a powerful tax system, which was extremely crucial for the country's economic development. Thus, the Goods and Services Tax stands to benefit the Indian economy [4].

Different industries faced challenges during the GST implementation because they were not prepared for GST, the pricing of their goods and services, credit transition, IT system, and

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operational issues related to return filing and refund claims. However, as time passed, every trader was prepared to comply with the GST tax regime [5]. The actual effect of any economy on the general public is when the prices of their necessities are affected. For them, the economy is in fine condition when prices for everyday goods and services become low. When inflation is too high, the public becomes dissatisfied with the changes made by the government. As a result, public satisfaction is essential for the successful implementation of any government policy, as without it, the policy will not succeed in the manner intended by the government [6, 15].

LITERATURE REVIEW:

Since the GST is a method of collecting tax revenue for the government, it has an impact on contemporary societies. Many scholars expressed their perspectives on GST implementation and the taxation system. A few scholars have contributed their understanding of GST implementation and its possible impact on the common man, which is shown in the table below.

Table 1: Exhibits the contribution by different authors in GST implication and effect on common man.

Sl No	Focus	Outcome	References
1	Negative and positive impact of GST to the society	The significance of GST is that all goods and services are taxed fairly. A single tax for one India is a game changer in a positive way that benefits not only the common man, but the country as a whole.	[2]
2	GST & its impact on Indian economy	The GST is on its way to integrating state economies and boosting overall economic growth. Incorporation of goods and services taxation would provide India with a world-class tax system and raise tax revenue.	[3]
3	GST implementation on common man	As a result, the study expressed the opinion as whenever a new reform or law is enacted in a country, it undoubtedly has an impact on the common man. As there is no exception for the common man, they had to prepare for the consequences.	[6]
4	GST – Biggest tax reforms in India	According to the study, a radical shift in traders' mindsets and attitudes toward tax payers, as well as a robust and comprehensive IT infrastructure, are required to support successful implementation. The study also focused on the government's appropriate steps for collecting GST from all assesseees who are subject to GST rules.	[7]
5	Consumers' Awareness and Its Impact of GST	Based on the study, all groups of people, including different age groups, were aware of GST and its implementation. Respondents who run businesses believe that the implementation of GST will have a significant impact.	[8, 18]
6	Growth of Revenue of GST	GST may have a beneficial impact on the economy; however, the four-tier structure of tax rates under GST may cause significant price increases for luxurious goods and services; furthermore, the government has made efforts to place necessities under the lowest tax rate slab.	[9]

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7	Impact of the GST implementation on GST Audit	Tax Compliance Behavior has a greater impact on GST Audit than Tax Complexity. As a result of the complex nature of GST legislation and regulations, as well as GST regulatory costs, the image of GST tax fairness may suffer. This demonstrates that there is a link between Tax Compliance Behavior and Tax Policy Fairness and Tax Complexity.	[10, 17]
8	Assessment of the Impact of Covid-19 on GST Collection	GST is a significant indicator that, along with other economic parameters, can be used to evaluate the condition of the economy. The drop in GST collection during pandemics emphasizes the necessity of creating a sustainable economic model based on advanced concepts in order to maintain stable economic growth during such disasters.	[11]

OBJECTIVES FOR THE STUDY:

- To understand the 47th GST Council Meeting Outcomes on Common man.
- To differentiate previous GST rate and with the New rate.
- To comprehend the impact of GST new rate on society.

ANALYSIS OF GST ON COMMON MAN POCKET ON THE BASIS OF EXPENDITURE:

The implementation of new Goods and Services Tax (GST) rates as per the 47th GST Council Meeting connects all sectors of the Indian economic system to face the inflationary scenario by creating a single unified tax [16]. People in the country are having a mixed reaction. The Goods and Services Tax (GST) is a destination-based tax on the consumption of Goods and Services that is levied at all stages, from manufacture to final consumption, with set-off for taxes paid at previous stages [12].

Thus, whenever any new reform or law is imposed in a country, it surely leaves its impact on the common man. So, as there is no exception to the common man, they had to get ready for the implications [13].

Key Changes in the GST Rates for Goods, w.e.f. July 18, 2022			
Goods	Existing GST rate	New GST rate	Difference
Printing, writing, or drawing ink	12 percent	18 percent	6 percent increased
Power-driven pumps primarily designed for handling water. For example, centrifugal pumps, deep tube-well turbine pumps, submersible pumps, and bicycle pumps	12 percent	18 percent	6 percent increased
LED lamps, lights and fixture, and their metal printed circuits board	12 percent	18 percent	6 percent increased
Drawing and marking out instruments	12 percent	18 percent	6 percent increased
Solar water heater and system	5 percent	12 percent	7 percent increased
Prepared/finished leather, chamois leather,	5 percent	12	7 percent

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composition leather		percent	increased
Orthopedic appliances – splints and other fracture appliances, artificial parts of the body, or other appliances that are worn or carried, or implanted in the body to compensate for a defect or disability, intraocular lens	12 percent	5 percent	7 percent reduced
Ostomy appliances	12 percent	5 percent	7 percent reduced
Tetra packs (aseptic packaging paper)	12 percent	18 percent	6 percent increased
Cut and polished diamonds	0.25 percent	1.5 percent	1.25 percent increased
Cheques, lose or in book form	NIL	18 percent	18 percent charged
Petroleum/coal bed methane	5 percent	12 percent	7 percent increased
E-waste	5 percent	18 percent	8 percent increased
Maps and hydrographic or similar charts of all kinds, including atlases, wall maps, topographical plans and globes	NIL	12 percent	12 percent charged

Source: India-briefing.com/news [13].

Clarifications with respect to GST Rates on Goods	
Sl. No.	Description
1.	Refund of accumulated input tax credit (ITC) shall not be allowed on edible oils and coal.
2.	Electric vehicles, whether or not fitted with a battery pack, are eligible for the concessional GST rate of five percent.
3.	Sewage treated water is not the same as purified water and hence exempt from GST.
4.	Nicotine polarilex gum attracts GST at 18 percent.

Source: India-briefing.com/news [13].

Withdrawal of GST exemption	
Sl. No.	Description
1.	Transportation by rail or vessel of railway equipment and material.
2.	Storage or warehousing of commodities which attract tax (nuts, spices, copra, jaggery, cotton etc.)
3.	Fumigation in a warehouse of agricultural produce.
4.	Services by Reserve Bank of India (RBI), Insurance Regulatory and Development Authority (IRDA), Securities and Exchange Board of India (SEBI), Food Safety and Standards Authority of India (FSSAI) and Goods and Services Tax Network (GSTN).

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5.	Renting of residential dwelling to registered business entities.
6.	Services provided by cord blood banks by way of preservation of stem cells.

Source: India-briefing.com/news [13].

Key Changes in the GST Rates for Services, w.e.f. July 18, 2022			
Services	Existing GST rate	New GST rate	Difference
Services supplied by foreman to chit fund	12 percent	18 percent	6 percent increased
Job work in relation to processing of hides, skins and leather	5 percent	12 percent	7 percent increased
Job work in relation to manufacture of leather goods and footwear	5 percent	12 percent	7 percent increased
Job work in relation to manufacture of clay bricks	5 percent	12 percent	7 percent increased
Works contract for roads, bridges, railways, metro, effluent treatment plant etc.	12 percent	18 percent	6 percent increased
Works contract service supplied to Central and State governments, local authorities for historical monuments, canals, dams, pipelines, plants for water supply, educational institutions, hospitals etc. and its sub-contracting	12 percent	18 percent	6 percent increased
Works contract service supplied to Central and State governments and local authorities involving predominantly earthwork and its sub-contracting	5 percent	12 percent	7 percent increased
Transport of goods and passengers by ropeways	18 percent	5 percent (with ITC for services)	8 percent reduced
Renting of truck/ goods carriage where cost of fuel is included	18 percent	12 percent	6 percent reduced

Source: India-briefing.com/news [13].

Clarifications with respect to GST Rates on Services	
Sl. No.	Description
1.	GST exemption on transport of passengers by air to and from North-eastern states and Bagdogra is restricted to economy class.
2.	Common bio-medical waste treatment facilities for treatment or disposal of biomedical waste shall be taxed at 12 percent with ITC benefit.
3.	Hotel accommodation of value up to INR 1000 per day shall be taxed at 12 percent.
4.	Room rent (excluding ICU) charged by a hospital, exceeding INR 5,000 per day per patient shall be taxed. The tax shall be levied only on the room rentals at five percent without ITC.
5.	GST exemption on training or coaching in recreational activities relating to arts, culture or sports is restricted only when supplied by an individual.

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6.	Fee charged by universities for issuance of migration certificate or eligibility certificate for admission is exempt from GST.
7.	Services associated with transit cargo both to and from Nepal and Bhutan are covered by exemption under entry 9B of notification No. 12/2017-CT(R).
8.	Activity of selling of space for advertisement in souvenirs published in the form of books is eligible for concessional GST at five percent.
9.	Renting of vehicle with operator for transportation of goods on time basis attracts GST at 18 percent. GST on such renting, where cost of fuel is included in the consideration charged will be taxable at 12 percent.
10.	Allowing choice of location of a plot is part of supply of long-term lease of the plot of land. Therefore, location charge or preferential location charges are part of consideration charged for long-term lease of land and shall get the same treatment under GST.
11.	Services in the form of assisted reproductive technology/in vitro fertilization covered under the definition of health care services for the purpose of exemption under GST.
12.	Sale of land after levelling, laying down of drainage lines, etc., is sale of land and would not attract GST.
13.	Renting of motor vehicles for transport of passengers to a body corporate for a period taxable in the hands of body corporate under reverse charge mechanism.
14.	Services provided by the guest anchors to TV channels in lieu of honorarium attract GST.

Source: [India-briefing.com/news](https://india-briefing.com/news) [13].

IMPACT OF GST ON SEVERAL SECTORS:

The implementation of GST new rates had an impact on consumable goods, hospitals, hotels, banking services, and other items subject to the GST tax regime [14]. The following are the changes effected to a common man for the rates of various items as a result of the implementation of the new GST rates as per the 47th GST council Meeting:

Taxable at 5% -

Curd; Lassi; Butter milk; Chena or paneer; Natural honey; Dried makhana; Rice; Wheat and meslin, Rye; Barley; Oats; Maize Corn; Grain sorghum; Wheat or meslin flour; Buckwheat, millet and canary seed; other than cereals such as Jawar, Bajra, Ragi; Cereal flours other than of wheat or meslin i.e. maize (corn) flour, Rye flour; Cereal groats, meal and pellets, including suji and dalia; Dried leguminous vegetables; Meat and edible meat offal; Fish and crustaceans, molluscs and other aquatic invertebrates; Meal, powder, Flour flakes, granules and pellets of potatoes; Animal or vegetable fertilisers or organic fertilizers; Jaggery of all types; Khandsari Sugar Guts, Bladders And Stomachs Of Animals(Other Than Fish), Whole And Pieces Thereof, Fresh, Chilled, Frozen, Salted, In Brine, Dried Or Smoked; Meal and powder of the dried leguminous vegetables of heading 0713 (pulses) other than guar meal and guar gum refined split, of sago or of roots or tubers

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or of the products; Puffed rice (Muri), flattened or beaten rice (Chira), parched rice(Khoi), parched paddy or rice coated with sugar or gur (Murki).

Taxable at 12% -

- Tender coconut water, Manioc, arrowroot, salep, Jerusalem artichokes, sweet potatoes and similar roots and tubers with high starch or inulin content, frozen, whether or not sliced or in the form of pellets.
- Maps and similar charts of all kinds, including atlases, wall maps, topographical plans and globes, printed: earlier exempted, now taxable @12%.
- Mangoes (other than mangoes sliced, dried), earlier exempted, now taxable at 12%.

Taxable at 18% -

- Blades, paper-cutting scissors, pencil sharpeners, spoons, forks, ladles, skimmers, and cake-servers: GST increased from 12% to 18%.
- Cheque books or cheques in loose form issued by banks: earlier exempted, now taxable @18%.
- GST on LED lamps and LED lights increased from 12% to 18%.

GST rate on services:

Withdrawal of exemption:

- Hotel rooms with less than ₹1,000 per day, which was earlier exempted, is now taxable @ 12%.
- Rooms provided by clinical establishments (except ICU/CCU/ICCU/NICU) having room charges exceeding ₹ 5000/- per day per patient which was earlier exempted is now taxable @ 5%.
- Residential dwelling rented to a registered person, taxable under reverse charge mechanism.
- Services provided by a GTA where freight upto Rs. 1500 for single consignment carriage and freight upto Rs. 750 per consignment for multiple consignment carriage.
- Transportation by rail/vessel of railway equipment and material.
- Storage or warehousing of nuts, spices, copra, sugarcane, Jaggery, cotton, flax, jute, indigo, unmanufactured tobacco, betel leaves, tendu leaves, coffee and tea.
- Treatment or disposal of biomedical waste or the processes incidental thereto by a common bio-medical waste treatment facility to a clinical establishment withdrawn and now it would be taxable @ 12%.
- Services provided by department of post irrespective of the status of recipient, taxable under reverse charge mechanism.
- Services provided by the RBI, IRDAI, SEBI, FSSAI, GSTN.
- Services provided by way of fumigation in a warehouse of agricultural produce.
- Services by way of training or coaching in recreational activities relating to arts or culture provided by persons other than an individual.

FINDINGS:

- Customers must pay more for their purchases as GST rates rise. As a result, a consumer's purchasing power has decreased. Due to the high tax on consumable items, it will make wage employees' pockets lighter.
- The ordinary citizen must pay more for household items, banking services, hospitals, and hotels, among other things.
- As a result of withdrawal of certain necessities, the common man's way of life has become more expensive.

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- Retailers, on the other hand, are losing their product market. Their income decreased as a result of covid effects and rising tax rates.
- Despite new GST amendments, traders are finding ways to evade tax.
- It was discovered that, while GST is a burden in the short term, GST is required to make our country financially strong in the long run as we are facing into inflation.

SUGGESTIONS:

- The common man suffered greatly as a result of the GST levied on consumables. Based on the facts, we can conclude that, while GST has caused hardship for the common citizen, it is ultimately beneficial to the nation in dealing with high inflation; otherwise, economists believe that India risks becoming the next neighbouring country.
- Organize several seminars to educate the general public about the new GST rates and their importance to the nation.
- To develop India's Infrastructure, Defense, Manufacturing Industries tax is the source to government so GST helps a lot.

CONCLUSION:

While such decisions on GST rate changes and exemption withdrawals are consistent to compensate for 'inefficiencies' in the value chain and increase the revenue-neutral rate, such decisions come at a time when the common man and the economy are reeling under high inflationary pressures, Considering the big picture, one wonders if this is the right time for such an exercise, given India's high inflation and geopolitical tensions.

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